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Customer preference and purchase intention in the footwear section at the Calapan city public market

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Abstract

Offering a high-quality product that leaves a positive impression on customers is the method of promotion used in the footwear industry. Marketers employ a variety of factors to influence consumers' decisions, but it is crucial to identify the elements that influence consumers' preferences when buying footwear, particularly in the public market of Calapan City. The need to determine the factors that affect the consumers' preference in purchasing footwear is very important in developing their marketing strategy. This situation encourage the researchers to assess the customer preference and purchase intention in the footwear section at the Calapan City public market. Data from a sample of 396 respondents was gathered for this study utilizing survey questionnaires and a quantitative descriptive approach. The results showed that while preferences differed significantly by age, gender, occupation, and education, price, product attributes, and purchasing channels all had a major impact on purchase decisions. Whereas older and less educated people valued price and accessibility, younger, more educated consumers were more interested in trends and digital platforms. A significant relationship was observed between consumer preferences and purchase intentions, with digital accessibility and competitive pricing emerging as key drivers. Based on the findings, the researchers recommend that footwear businesses adopt competitive pricing, enhance online platforms, and align product offerings with seasonal trends and generational values to attract and retain customers effectively.

Keywords: Customer Preference; Footwear Shops; Purchase Intention; Customer Profile; Generation; Theory of Price

1. Introduction

Customers' preferences, technological improvements, and market conditions have all contributed to substantial changes in the footwear industry. Footwear has transitioned from a necessity to a lifestyle thing. According to [1] personal, psychological, social, and cultural aspects influence client purchase decisions, as do pricing, trends, availability, and generational preferences. Footwear blends function, style, and cultural identity. It protects and supports the foot, promotes health and comfort, and allows for personal and cultural expression. Quality footwear reduces health risks and increases brand loyalty, demonstrating its value in everyday life.

Footwear merchants at Calapan City Public Market offer a wide range of alternatives, from sneakers to formal shoes, to meet a variety of demands and budgets. The market is noted for its affordability and ability to haggle prices, making it a cost-effective and fun shopping experience. Malls, which provide branded merchandise, comfortable surroundings, and after-sales services, pose a significant challenge to public marketplaces. However, markets continue to be competitive by delivering locally created, inexpensive footwear and a unique. In the footwear section in Calapan City public market, most vendors do not have the knowledge regarding consumer behavior and purchase intention of the diverse customers. Inventory management is made more difficult by issues including varying client profiles and

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inaccurate demand projections. The need for specialized studies is highlighted by the rareness of research highlighting the need for localized studies linking consumer profiles to purchase decisions.

The purpose of this study is to look at how consumer demographics influence their preferences and buy intentions in the footwear department of the Calapan City Public Market. Specifically, it seeks to: explore the demographic profiles of respondents in terms of age, gender, occupation, and educational level; assess the extent to which factors such as price, trends, features, availability, generation, and channels influence customer preferences; determine the current level of purchase intention among customers; and evaluate whether significant differences exist in customer preferences when grouped by demographic variables. In addition, this study is led by the following null hypotheses: H01 states that there is no significant variation in the amount of purchase intention across respondents based on their profiles. H02 indicates that there is no significant association between the level of buy intention and the factors influencing consumer preference. By addressing these assumptions and research questions, the study hopes to provide practical insights for improving marketing strategies in the footwear department of the Calapan City Public Market.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1. Customer Preference

According to [2] customer preferences significantly influence decision-making processes by acting as criteria for evaluating products and services. These preferences, shaped by cultural, social, and psychological factors, determine which features or attributes customers prioritize in their purchasing decisions [3] found a strong link between customer preferences and purchase intention. Positive attitudes toward a product, aligned with preferences, increase purchase likelihood. Personalized marketing enhances trust and brand credibility, further driving purchase intention.

- *Price*

[4] emphasized that price sensitivity often determines where customers shop and what products they purchase. Retailers frequently use price promotions to increase store traffic and encourage purchases. [5] identified that price impacts both purchase intentions and decisions, particularly when combined with product quality. Price also acted as an intervening variable, emphasizing its role in shaping consumer behavior. [6] found that price contributes to repurchase intentions for outdoor products, particularly when mediated by Customer Perceived Value (CPV). Consumers weigh price against perceived benefits, demonstrating its influence on purchase behavior.

- *Trends*

Trends play a significant role in shaping consumer purchase intentions, particularly in industries like fashion and footwear, where younger generations are heavily influenced by the latest societal and fashion trends. Research shows that traditional purchase factors such as price and quality are being overtaken by social media engagement and electronic word-of-mouth (E-WOM) [7] Emerging trends like the integration of AI, chatbots, and parasocial interactions are also reshaping consumer expectations in the digital age [8] Additionally, digital promotions and technology-driven strategies, especially during the pandemic, have boosted repurchase intentions [9] In industries like beauty, trends driven by social media promotions and brand reputation play a crucial role in maintaining consumer interest [10] . Platforms like Instagram and TikTok have been found to drive impulse purchases, with FOMO playing a major role [11]

- *Features*

Product features significantly influence consumer purchase decisions by aligning with their preferences and needs, with attributes like functionality, usability, and innovation making a product more appealing and distinguishing it from competitors. Research has shown that features such as labeling, freshness, and durability in seafood products help build consumer trust and enhance market competitiveness [12] In smartphones, key features like camera quality, battery life, and screen resolution are particularly important for Gen Z consumers in the Philippines [13], while in cars, engine performance, fuel efficiency, and safety are major factors for purchase decisions [14]. Eco-friendly features like sustainability also play a growing role in influencing purchase intentions among environmentally-conscious consumers [15]. Additionally, innovative features contribute to product perceptions, blending emotional and practical value [16], and advanced functionalities strengthen brand loyalty [17] Consumer priorities may shift between functionality and convenience depending on time constraints [18], and features like design, comfort, and quality in footwear reflect personality traits and influence purchasing choices [19].

- *Availability*

Availability refers to the ease of access to products and its influence on consumer purchase intentions. [20] in their study "Making Sustainable Consumption Decisions," demonstrated that availability is a key determinant of consumer willingness to purchase sustainable products. Increasing product availability can significantly enhance consumer trust and sales. [21] highlighted the importance of offering alternative products when primary items are unavailable. This strategy helps retain consumer interest and fosters loyalty. Lastly, [22] found that consistent product availability plays a critical role in influencing purchase decisions for commodity products like construction materials, demonstrating its universal importance across industries.

- *Generation*

Generational differences significantly influence consumer preferences, decision-making processes, and purchase intentions. [23] observed that Generation Y prioritizes brand image and unique product features in their sneaker purchase decisions, whereas price plays a less significant role. In contrast, [24] highlighted the importance of trust and social influence in shaping Generation Z's purchasing behaviors

- *Channels*

Channels are the platforms or methods through which products are offered to consumers, significantly shaping shopping behaviors. [25] highlighted the role of competitive pricing and user-friendly platforms like Shopee in influencing Filipino online shopping behaviors. Similarly, [26] demonstrated that physical stores remain essential for categories requiring in-person evaluation. [27] found that convenience and affordability drive Filipino consumers' preference for online channels, while [28] observed that e-commerce platforms have reshaped traditional retail models by offering a wider consumer base to small businesses.

- *Purchase Intention*

Purchase intention reflects a customer's willingness to buy a product and serves as a key predictor of actual purchasing behavior [29] It is closely linked to customer profiles, as demographic, psychographic, and behavioral data help identify factors influencing intent and enable targeted marketing to high-potential groups [30] Additionally, customer preferences significantly shape purchase intention, as products aligned with these preferences increase satisfaction and reduce decision-making uncertainty, thereby boosting the likelihood of purchase [31]). Understanding these relationships is crucial for businesses to craft effective strategies.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

- *Theory of Price*

The theory of price, as explained by [32] asserts that the price of a good or service is determined by the balance between supply and demand, with prices rising when demand exceeds supply and falling when supply surpasses demand. [33] further emphasizes that the optimal market price, or equilibrium, is achieved when the amount consumers are willing to pay aligns with the cost of production. This microeconomic principle highlights the importance of understanding the delicate balance between supply and demand, which is crucial for businesses to develop effective pricing strategies, adapt to market changes, and maintain competitiveness. By mastering this equilibrium, businesses can refine their pricing approaches to meet customer preferences and create a stable market environment that benefits both producers and consumers [34]

2.2.1. Theory of Customer Choice

The theory of customer choice, as explained by [35] explores how individuals make decisions about their spending based on their limited resources, like money and time, to fulfill their needs and desires. This theory helps explain market behavior and guides economic policies by examining the factors that influence customer preferences. It is based on three main assumptions: first, people make purchasing decisions to maximize their satisfaction, known as utility maximization; second, individuals are never fully satisfied, meaning they always desire more, a concept called the principle of non-satiation; and third, while consuming more may increase happiness, the additional satisfaction diminishes with each extra unit, referred to as declining marginal utility.

- *Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)*

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), introduced by [36], explains how purchase intentions are influenced by an individual's attitudes, social pressures, and perceived ability to make the purchase. In the case of footwear, a consumer

may form a positive view of a brand based on its comfort, quality, or design. Social influences, such as the opinions of friends or online reviews, can further encourage this intention. Additionally, if the purchase is perceived as convenient, affordable, and easy to complete, the likelihood of making the purchase increases. This theory integrates cognitive, social, and practical factors to clarify how consumer behavior impacts buying decisions.

2.3. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework below presents the relationship between various factors influencing customer preferences, demographic profile, and purchase intention.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

The demographic profile, which includes factors such as age, gender, occupation, and educational level, acts as the independent variable and can significantly influence how consumers perceive and interact with products. These demographics provide valuable insights into customer behavior, which are crucial for understanding the factors that influence purchase decisions. The dependent variable, on the other hand, is the factors affecting customers' purchase intention, including trends, features, price, availability, generation, and channels. These factors may vary depending on the customers' demographic characteristics, meaning that individuals with different age groups, genders, occupations, and educational backgrounds may respond differently. According to [37] understanding these factors is essential as consumer spending becomes increasingly important in the global economy. The research aims to develop a marketing plan focused on improving consumer engagement and sales, by tailoring strategies to different target market segments to better address their specific needs and preferences, ultimately boosting sales.

2.4. Statement of the Problem

This study aims to identify the effect of customer profiles on customer preferences and purchase intentions in the footwear section at the Calapan City Public Market. It seeks to answer the following questions:

- *What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:*
 - Age,
 - Gender,
 - Occupation, and
 - Educational level?
- *As assessed by customers in the footwear section at the Calapan City Public Market, to what extent are the factors of customer preference manifested in terms of:*
 - Price,
 - Trends,
 - Features,
 - Availability,
 - Generation, and
 - Channels

- What is the current level of purchase intention among customers in footwear shops in Calapan City Public Market?
- Is there significant difference among the factors of customer preference when grouped according to profile variables?
- Is there a significant relationship between the level of purchase intention and factors of customer preference?

2.5. Hypothesis

- H01: There is no significant difference in the level of purchase intention when group according to their profile
- H02: There is no significant relationship between the level of purchase intention and factors of customer preference

3. Material and methods

3.1. Research Design

The study employed a quantitative descriptive design to explore individuals' perspectives and behaviors. A survey questionnaire was used to collect data, systematically defining the problem and proposing solutions. Primary and secondary sources were utilized to gather information. The study examined trends, product attributes, pricing, product availability, and age variations influencing footwear purchase intentions, with the aim of proposing effective marketing strategies.

3.2. Respondents and Sampling

The population comprised 41,760 customers from six selected footwear stores in Calapan City. Slovin's formula determined a sample size of 396 respondents with a 5% margin of error. Simple random sampling ensured an unbiased and representative sample. This approach minimized bias and reduced the margin of error, enhancing the reliability of the results.

The questionnaire was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, which measures the internal consistency of the items in the questionnaire.

Table 1 Reliability and Validity Test of Survey Questionnaire

Reliability Analysis			
Indicators	Cronbach Alpha Value	Number of Items	Interpretation
Price	0.772	5	Acceptable
Trends	0.830	5	Good
Features	0.790	5	Acceptable
Availability	0.891	5	Good
Generation	0.835	5	Good
Channel	0.776	5	Acceptable
Current Level of Purchase Intention	0.869	5	Good
<i>George and Mallery (2003) provide the following rules of thumb:</i>			
<i>"_ > .9 - Excellent, _ > .8 - Good, _ > .7 - Acceptable, _ > .6 - Questionable, _ > .5 - Poor, and _ < .5 - Unacceptable"</i>			

The reliability analysis shows that all the indicators have Cronbach Alpha values above 0.7, meaning they are at least acceptable. "Trends," "Availability," "Generation," and "Current Level of Purchase Intention" are rated as good with values above 0.8. The others—"Price," "Features," and "Channel"—fall within the acceptable range (above 0.7 but below 0.8). Based on George and Mallery's rules, these results suggest the indicators have consistent reliability, suitable for research use.

3.3. Data Gathering Procedures and Instrumentation

Data were collected through a self-structured survey questionnaire, designed using a Likert scale to measure responses accurately. The questionnaires were distributed in person, and responses were analyzed. The reliability of the questionnaire was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, with all indicators scoring above 0.7, signifying acceptable to good reliability.

3.4. Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including frequency and percentage distribution, were used to analyze respondents' demographic profiles. Weighted mean measured central tendencies, ANOVA tested differences in variables, and correlation analysis determined relationships between variables.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 Result of Demographic Profile of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18 and below	91	23.0
19-30 years old	96	24.2
31-40 years old	84	21.2
41-50 years old	69	17.4
Above 51 years old	56	14.1
Gender		
Male	188	47.5
Female	208	52.5
Occupation		
Student	116	29.3
Employed (Private Sector)	60	15.2
Employed (Government Sector)	70	17.7
Self-employed	83	21.0
Unemployed	67	16.9
Educational Attainment		
Elementary Level	30	7.6
Highschool Level	99	25.0
College Level	145	36.6
Postgraduate (Master's/Doctorate)	70	17.7
Vocational/Technical Graduate	52	13.1

The age distribution shows that most respondents are aged 19-30 (24.2%) and 18 and below (23.0%), followed by 31-40 (21.2%), 41-50 (17.4%), and above 51 (14.1%). Gender representation is nearly equal, with females at 52.5% and males at 47.5%, ensuring balanced perspectives.

Students make up the largest occupational group (29.3%), followed by self-employed individuals (21.0%), government employees (17.7%), private-sector workers (15.2%), and unemployed individuals (16.9%). Educational attainment is

led by college-level respondents (36.6%), with high school (25.0%), postgraduates (17.7%), vocational graduates (13.1%), and elementary-level individuals (7.6%) following.

4.2. Extent of Influence of Factors on Purchase Intention

Table 3 Summary on the Extent of Influence of Factors of Purchase Intention

Statements	Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
Price	3.23	1	Influential
Trends	3.04	5	Influential
Features	3.18	2	Influential
Availability	3.13	4	Influential
Generation	3.02	6	Influential
Channels	3.17	3	Influential
Overall Mean	3.11		Influential
<i>Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 – Most Influential; 2.50 – 3.24 – Influential; 1.75 – 2.49 Moderately Influential; 1.00 – 1.74 – Least Influential</i>			

Price ranked highest (mean = 3.23), indicating that the cost of products plays the most important role in consumer decisions. Features (mean = 3.18) and Channels (mean = 3.17) follow, showing that product attributes like usability and the convenience of purchasing platforms also strongly impact buying behavior. Availability (mean = 3.13) and Trends (mean = 3.04) rank slightly lower, suggesting that while consumers value access to products and staying updated with trends, these factors are not as influential as price or features. Generation (mean = 3.02) ranks the lowest, indicating that factors like cultural relevance or brand alignment with generational preferences are less impactful overall.

4.3. Current Level of Purchase Intention

Table 4 Level of Purchase Intention

Statements	Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
I am most likely to purchase footwear from the shops of public market. in the future	2.74	5	Influential
I am probably buying footwear in the public market.	2.98	3	Influential
I am willing to buy on these footwear shop thorough an online platform	3.58	1	Most Influential
I intend to recommend these footwear shops to my friends and family.	2.80	4	Influential
I am willing to transact in these footwear shop using online payment.	3.44	2	Most Influential
Overall Mean	3.11		Influential
<i>Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 – Most Influential; 2.50 – 3.24 – Influential; 1.75 – 2.49 Moderately Influential; 1.00 – 1.74 – Least Influential</i>			

The statement "I am willing to buy on these footwear shops through an online platform" ranked highest with a mean of 3.58, highlighting the strong influence of e-commerce on purchase intention due to its convenience and accessibility. This indicates that online platforms are a significant driver of purchase intention, reflecting consumer preference for the convenience and accessibility of digital shopping. The rise of e-commerce channels has likely made online platforms more appealing, especially among tech-savvy consumers [34] In contrast, "I am most likely to purchase footwear from the shops of the public market in the future" ranked lowest at 2.74, suggesting limited consumer preference for traditional market options. This suggests that while consumers acknowledge the public market as a purchase option, it is not their first choice compared to more convenient or innovative channels. Public markets may need to adapt to modern trends to sustain buyer interest [27]

With an overall mean of 3.11, the current level of purchase intention is moderately positive, driven by the appeal of online platforms and digital payment options. This aligns with the growing role of digital integration in enhancing customer engagement and influencing purchase decision. . [38] supported this by emphasizing the growing importance of digital integration in enhancing customer engagement and purchase intention

4.4. Differences in the Factors of Customers' preferences when grouped according to Profile Factors

Table 5 Differences in the Factors of Customers' preferences when grouped according to Profile Factors

Price	F-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age	2.706	0.030	Significant	Reject
Gender	0.423	0.516	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Occupation	1.047	0.038	Significant	Reject
Educational Level	2.174	0.071	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Trends				
Age	1.436	0.021	Significant	Reject
Gender	0.933	0.335	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Occupation	0.673	0.611	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Educational Level	3.138	0.315	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Features				
Age	2.111	0.079	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Gender	0.476	0.049	Significant	Reject
Occupation	0.432	0.786	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Educational Level	2.664	0.032	Significant	Reject
Availability				
Age	2.035	0.089	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Gender	.319	0.573	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Occupation	.503	0.033	Significant	Reject
Educational Level	2.069	0.084	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Generation				
Age	5.281	<.001	Significant	Reject
Gender	0.024	0.876	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Occupation	0.447	0.212	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Educational Level	2.982	0.019	Significant	Reject
Channels				
Age	3.679	0.006	Significant	Reject
Gender	0.622	0.431	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Occupation	0.794	0.029	Significant	Reject
Educational Level	3.838	0.005	Significant	Reject

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.05; R – Rejected; FR – Failed to Reject; S – Significant; NS – Not Significant

Younger consumers are more price-sensitive due to limited finances, while older consumers prioritize quality, aligning with [39] findings on financial capacity influencing pricing preferences. Occupations also affect price perceptions due to varying income levels. Trends differ by age ($p = 0.021$), with younger individuals being more trend-driven via social media, while older consumers prefer reliability [10].

Feature preferences vary by gender ($p = 0.049$) and education ($p = 0.032$), with men valuing functionality, women aesthetics, and higher education encouraging critical product evaluation [40]. Availability preferences differ by occupation ($p = 0.033$), as busy individuals prioritize accessibility [41]. Channels also vary significantly by age ($p = 0.006$), occupation ($p = 0.029$), and education ($p = 0.005$), with younger, tech-savvy individuals favoring online platforms, as noted by [38] and [42]

4.5. Relationship between the Level of purchase intention and Factors of Customer Preference

Table 6 Correlation Analysis between Level of Purchase Intention and Factors of Customer Preference

Level of Purchase Intention				
Factors of Costumer Preference	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Price	.306**	<.001	Significant	Reject
Trends	.246**	<.001	Significant	Reject
Features	.252**	<.001	Significant	Reject
Availability	.256**	<.001	Significant	Reject
Generation	.312**	<.001	Significant	Reject
Channels	.342**	<.001	Significant	Reject
Legend: Significant at p -value < 0.05; R – Rejected; FR – Failed to Reject; S – Significant; NS – Not Significant **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				

Price ($p < 0.001$) significantly correlates with purchase intention, showing that affordability strongly influences consumer decisions, especially for budget-conscious buyers [43] Trends ($p < 0.001$) also play a key role, as consumers favor products that align with the latest styles, particularly younger demographics [44].

Features ($p < 0.001$) and availability ($p < 0.001$) also significantly impact purchase intention, with functional designs enhancing perceived value [45] and accessibility reducing barriers to purchase [46]. Generational preferences ($p < 0.001$) and channels ($p < 0.001$) show the strongest correlations, reflecting the influence of cultural values and the convenience of online platforms on consumer behavior[47]These findings reject the null hypothesis, confirming that price, trends, features, availability, generation, and channels significantly drive purchase intention.

5. Conclusion

The study reveals that respondents are predominantly young, with balanced gender representation and a majority having college-level education or higher. Students form the largest group, followed by self-employed and employed individuals. Price is the most influential factor in purchase decisions, followed by product features and purchasing channels, while availability and trends hold moderate importance. Purchase intention is moderately positive, but consumers increasingly favor online shopping and digital payments for convenience.

Preferences differ by age, education, occupation, and gender, with younger and more educated individuals favoring trends and digital platforms, while older and less-educated respondents prioritize practicality and accessibility. The findings emphasize the importance of competitive pricing, digital accessibility, and trend alignment to attract consumers. This study provides valuable insights for businesses to align strategies with consumer preferences, benefiting society by promoting market innovation and inclusivity.

Recommendation

Based on the findings the researchers recommend the following:

Footwear business owners are advised to adopt competitive pricing strategies, such as discounts, promotions, and

bundle deals, to attract budget-conscious consumers while maintaining quality. Leveraging online platforms with multiple payment options like mobile wallets and bank transfers, alongside live shopping events on social media, can boost engagement and sales. Emphasizing product innovation, durability, and aesthetic appeal while aligning releases with seasonal trends ensures relevance and consumer satisfaction. Additionally, maintaining adequate inventory levels for popular sizes and styles, and offering a diverse product range, minimizes stockouts and encourages repeat purchases. Implementing strategic marketing practices will further enhance sales, customer satisfaction, and overall market presence.

For future researchers, it is recommended to explore psychological and emotional factors influencing purchase decisions, such as consumer trust, loyalty, and perceived brand value. Investigating how these variables interact with consumer preferences can provide deeper insights into developing effective business strategies and understanding market dynamics.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest or competing interests related to the publication of this manuscript. The study is unique and has not been influenced by any institution, organization, or product mentioned in the manuscript, nor is it associated with any competing products or interests. The findings and conclusions presented are the sole work of the authors and are free from any bias or external influence.

Statement of ethical approval

The present research work does not involve any studies performed on animals or human subjects. Data were collected solely through a self-structured survey questionnaire, and no experimental treatment or intervention was conducted. The study adhered to ethical research standards, ensuring the confidentiality and voluntary participation of all respondents.

Statement of informed consent

A letter of informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation in the study. Respondents were fully informed about the purpose of the research, the voluntary nature of their participation, and the measures taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity of their responses.

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